

Politeness in Aviation Communications through the Speech Act of Request: A Case at Vietnam Aviation Academy

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ABSTRACT: In the current context of international integration, English is one of the most widely used languages which serves as a common means of professional communications. In aviation communications, English is considered as a lingua franca to express messages in suggestion, invitation and request between the passengers and airlines agents. Politeness in aviation communications is considered as an essential factor in evaluating airlines, however, there have been many complains about impolite communications; and that makes the airlines' images bad and less attractive. Polite use of English in aviation passenger service communications is essential, as politeness is a fundamental requirement in the aviation industry. Therefore, teaching and learning English as a foreign language for specific occupational purposes have become both urgent and essential. This study was scoped to look into the elements that influence politeness in aviation communications through speech act of request. The study carried out with mixed method through the tools of questionnaire, interviews with students and teachers, and classroom observation. It aimed at analyzing politeness in aviation communications through the speech act of request by investigating students' perception, attitudes, and desires towards the need for it; and teachers strategies in teaching it. The study results were discussed to find suggestions to obtain the higher quality of teaching and learning distinctive features of polite requests in aviation communications. This study also contributed as a reference for learners, teachers, airlines agents, and researchers in improving their knowledge of using English politely in requesting.

KEYWORDS: Politeness, Aviation Communications, Speech Act, Request.

I. INTRODUCTION

The aviation industry in Vietnam in particular, and worldwide in general, places great importance on politeness in communications between aviation staff and passengers. Politeness in communications is one of the essential issues addressed in the era of global integration. Politeness represents a link between language and the social world, so it is very necessary to minimize potential conflict and also to enhance individual's social relations. But in some cases, using polite forms may be misunderstood and unappreciated, especially among passengers and agents.

Through experience in teaching English to Vietnamese university students, especially at Vietnam Aviation Academy, the author has observed that Vietnamese students, in certain situations, use English expressions that are not appropriate to English communications styles or to the required specific levels of politeness.

Vietnam's aviation industry is still relatively young compared to that of other countries; therefore, it requires further research for improvement and development its fields. Today, most aviation research has focused on technical and economic aspects, while little attention has been paid to communicative language used in passenger services communications. Thus, this topic may be one of the first studies in Vietnam to examine politeness in aviation communications through the speech act of request. It is highly necessary for improving the quality of teaching and using Aviation English for passenger service staff. Such a study is essential and undoubtedly involves complex yet fascinating issues, which have motivated the author to undertake this research. For these reasons, the author has chosen the topic *Politeness in Aviation Communications through the Speech Act of Request: A case at Vietnam Aviation Academy* for this study.

As this study is limited to communications in airline passenger services, primarily through the listening–speaking channel, so it does not examine non-verbal communications (just focuses on verbal communications). The study concentrates on politeness as expressed in communicative situations in passenger services through the speech act of request.

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The research subjects are the ways politeness is expressed in aviation passenger service communications through speech act of request and how the Passengers Service students were taught and learnt it. The participants include students, and English teachers currently teaching at Vietnam Aviation Academy.

The aims of the study are:

1. To analyze politeness in aviation communications through the speech act of request.
2. To propose measures to enhance polite English communications skills through the speech act of request in class and in aviation passenger service environment.

To achieve these aims, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. To analyze students' perception, attitudes, and desires towards the need for politeness in aviation passenger service communications through the speech act of request and teachers strategies in teaching politeness communications.

Based on the research findings, what suggestions can help improve teaching and learning polite English communications skills in aviation passenger services through the speech act of request?

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Politeness

In linguistic communications, utterances may be judged as rude, impolite, polite, informal, formal, or tactful. The concept of politeness is used to study these evaluative effects.

Nguyễn Đức Dân (1998) emphasized that alongside the Cooperative Principle, the Politeness Principle plays a crucial role in shaping language structures and communicative behavior. Fraser (1990) identified four approaches to politeness: *Politeness as a social norm*, *Politeness as conversational maxims*, *Politeness as face-saving behavior (Brown & Levinson)*, *Politeness as a conversational contract*.

Lakoff (1977) defined politeness as mutual respect and proposes three rules: *Do not impose*; *Give options*; *Make the hearer feel good*. George Yule (1996) considered politeness as polite social behavior or etiquette within a culture.

2.2. Speech Act and The Speech Act of Request

A speech act is an utterance that performs an actions in a social context, rather than merely conveying information. It is a fundamental unit of communication in which speaking is considered a form of action. Speech acts are central to pragmatics, the study of language use in context, and highlight how meaning is shaped by social interaction rather than just truth condition.

According to J. L. Austin (1986) and John Searle (1971), speech acts can be analyzed at three levels:

- Locutionary act: The act of producing a meaningful expression, i.e., the literal utterance.
- Illocutionary act: The conventional force of the utterance, such as, asserting, requesting, promising, or warning.
- Perlocutionary act: The effect the utterance has on the listeners, such as persuading, amusing, or alarming them.

Later developments also include meta locutionary acts, which organize or comment on discourse itself, and direct speech acts, where one type of act is performed through another. (Britannica).

Speech acts are commonly categorized into five major types (EBSCO Research)

- Representatives: Statements that convey information or beliefs(e.g., asserting, describing)
- Directives: Attempts to get the listeners to do something (e.g., requesting, commanding)
- Commissive: Commitments by the speakers to future actions (e.g., promising, offering)
- Expressive: Expressions of the speaker's psychological state (e.g., apologizing, congratulating)
- Declarations: Utterances that bring about a chang in the external world by their very utterance (e.g., resigning, baptizing)

2.3. Communications and Characteristics of Aviation Passenger Service Communications

Communications is the process of exchanging information, ideas, or emotions between individuals or groups through verbal, non-verbal, written, or visual means. Communications involves a sender, a message, a medium, a receivers, and feedback.

The senders encodes a thought or idea into a message, which is transmitted through a chose channel. The receiver decodes the massage and provides feedback, completing the communications loop. Effective communications ensures that the intended meaning is understood, reducing misunderstandings and fostering collaboration. If not, breakdown communications will be led to. Language differences is one of the most common barriers to effective communications.

Aviation communications occurs between airline staff (ground service agents, flight attendants, pilots, airport staff, security officers, customs officers, etc.) and passengers of diverse ages, occupations, nationalities, and social backgrounds.

It is: business and service-oriented communications, conducted in public and collective settings, often brief but occurring across multiple stages (ticketing, check-in, boarding, in-flight, arrival), in situations of intercultural and international interaction.

Some characteristics of Aviation Passenger Service Communications include:

- Effective communication: Clear and transparent communication are essential for managing passengers 'expectation.

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- Personalized interactions: Personalized interactions make passengers feel valued and appreciated.

2.4. Previous studies and research gaps

Research on Politeness through the Speech Act has been conducted by many authors.

In Viet Nam

Nguyen Duc Dan (1998) summarized previous studies related to the Politeness Principle, including the work of Brown and Levinson (1987), who approached politeness as face-saving behavior, and Lakoff (1973, 1989) and Leech (1983), who viewed politeness as conversational maxims. Nguyen Thien Giap (2007) defined “face” as an individual’s public self-image, associated with social awareness and the desire to be recognized by others. Ta Thi Thanh Tam (2005) examined communicative roles and politeness in Vietnamese communications.

In global contexts

Crystal (1997) believed that politeness, in sociolinguistics and pragmatics, is a term that signifies linguistic features associated with norm of social behavior, in relation to notions like courtesy, rapport, deference and distance.

Eelen (2001) clarified that politeness, according to the Anglo-Saxon scientific tradition, is investigated from the pragmatic and sociolinguistic perspective. It is agreed that theories of politeness are involved in what belongs to either of these linguistic subfields. Politeness is specifically concerned with language use that is connected with pragmatics. It is a phenomenon that represents a link between language and the social world.

Brown and Levinson (1987) developed the concept of “face,” distinguishing between positive face and negative face.

Saeed (2009) added that the notion of face, as Brown and Levinson’s concept, is universal because every language community has a system of politeness.

Leech (1983) proposed that politeness involves one’s belief or perception about whether what one intends to say is polite or impolite. His Politeness Principle includes six maxims: Tact, Generosity, Approbation, Modesty, Agreement, and Sympathy.

In short, acts in communications such as requesting, initiating, ordering, warning and so on, can be accomplished by using language. Politeness is essentially associated with language use and plays an important role in verbal communications, especially in aviation

Currently, language communications in the aviation industry has also attracted attention from the UK Civil Aviation Authority, which has conducted research into the impact of inadequate English proficiency—the global language of aviation—on safety. Evidence suggests that Aviation English standards under ICAO regulations are not always met. This research program has been funded by the UK Department for Transport under the UK Safety Program.

Although numerous studies in Vietnamese and English have addressed politeness in pragmatics, no study to date has examined politeness through the speech act of request in aviation communications. Therefore, this study represents an initial attempt to explore politeness within professional aviation communications.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design

The study was conducted by following a mixed method research design, consisting both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The quantitative data was collected through a questionnaire, whereas the qualitative data was collected through one-on-one interviews with teachers and students. The classroom observation was conducted in 2 distinct classes of Aviation English for Passenger Services, with each class about 50 minutes.

3.2. Sampling

This study was conducted at Vietnam Aviation Academy, involving 45 students in 2 classes of Passengers services Students. These students have the same learning environments and cultural background.

The interview was conducted with 9 students, and 5 teachers who had at least 3 years of English teaching experiences. The observation of 2 classes was conducted during the course of Aviation English for Passengers services.

3.3. Instruments

The questionnaire, consists of 5 questions with 5-scale Likert responses, was divided into these sections: Students’ Perception of the need for politeness in aviation communications, Students’ Attitudes towards the need for politeness in aviation communications, and Students’ desires in learning about politeness in aviation communications in classroom.

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Statistics

		Students' Perception of The Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications	Students' Attitudes Towards the Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications	Students' desires in learning about Politeness in Aviation Communications in classroom
N	Valid	90	90	90
	Missing	0	0	0

One-on-one interviews with nine students (randomly chosen), were required to answer seven questions about the structures that they like utilizing to express politeness in communications.

Five teachers were taken part in interviews about their strategies in teaching polite requests. The author assured all information would be treated with strict confidentiality, and utilized exclusively for research purposes.

The classroom observation was conducted in distinct classes, with each class about 50 minutes spending in learning English for Passenger Services. The classroom observation sought to teaching and learning progress that focused on five issues and seven questions about polite structures. They are students' perception, students' attitudes, students' desire, students' preference on Types of Politeness Structures, and teachers' strategies in instructing students in politeness in aviation communications. The author observed the teachers' strategies in instructing students in politeness in aviation communications, and students' attitudes towards politeness in aviation communications. These classroom observation results were carefully treated and utilized exclusively for research purposes.

3.4. Data analysis

The responses from the questionnaire were collected and analyzed by using SPSS Version 20.0 for Windows. Data collected from the questionnaire were sorted and analyzed quantitatively using means standard deviations, and percentages. The mean ratings for students' perception based on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree". Responses from students and teachers were recorded and analyzed.

3.5. Ethical considerations

Through the course of the research, the following standards of the conduct were upheld. (i) No plagiarized materials from other these or related papers was used in the preparation of this thesis. All of the theories and papers were properly and completely extracted. (ii) The author consistently prioritized the dignity and welfare of our students. (iii) Aside from obtaining the students' consent to publish their real identities in the research report, all research data was kept anonymous throughout the study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Quantitative Results from questionnaires and discussion

Table 1 presented analysis of response on 3 statements. The first statement "Politeness is rather essential in Aviation Communications" got the response (F=10; P=11.1; VP=11.1) and the second one "Politeness is essential in Aviation Communications" got the highest level response (F=45; P=50.0; VP=50.0); whereas the third one "Politeness is very essential in Aviation Communications" got the medium level (F=35; P=38.9; VP=38.9). It indicated that, in some cases, communications between airlines agents and passengers just remain the standard of correct and adequate level, i.e. for harassing, angry, violent or before warned passengers.

Table 1: Students' Perception of The Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Politeness is rather essential in Aviation Communications	10	11.1	11.1	11.1
	Politeness is essential in Aviation Communications	45	50.0	50.0	61.1
	Politeness is very essential in Aviation Communications	35	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

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Figure 1: Students' Perception of The Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications

Table 2 presented 2 statements about Students' attitudes towards the need for politeness in aviation communications. The first statement received a higher level of agreements (F=70; P=77.8; VP=77.8) with the statement. The second obtained a lower level of agreement (F=20; P=22.2; VP=22.2). These results showed that most of the students were interested in politeness in aviation communications in any situations, i.e. from ground services to in-flight services, and even after-flight services.

Table 2: Students' Attitudes Towards the Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Communicating politely with the passengers in any situations	70	77.8	77.8	77.8
	Communicating politely with the passengers just in necessary situations	20	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2: Students' Attitudes Towards the Need for Politeness in Aviation Communications

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Table 3 presented Students' desires in learning about Politeness in Aviation Communications in classroom. The first statement "Like self -studying" just received a lowest level number (F=2; P= 2.2; VP= 2.2), and the second statement "Like receiving teachers' explanations" received a higher level number (F=6; P= 6.7; VP= 6.7). The highest level number statement was " Like role - playing after following the teachers' guide" (F=82; P= 91.1; VP= 91.1). This showed that role - playing followed teachers' explanations was students' most preference because it was necessary and interested.

Table 3: Students' desires in learning about Politeness in Aviation Communications in classroom

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid				
Like self -studying	2	2.2	2.2	2.2
Like receiving teachers' explanations	6	6.7	6.7	8.9
Like role - playing after following the teachers' guide	82	91.1	91.1	100.0
Total	90	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3: Students' desires in learning about Politeness in Aviation Communications in classroom

4.2. Qualitative Results and discussion from the interviews

This is the case summary of Qualitative Results from the interviews. The interview consisted of two types. Type 1 with the statement "Aviation Politeness Structures" was taken part in by 9 randomly chosen students to answer the question about Aviation Politeness Structures. The last one was conducted for the teachers to ask about the strategies they have utilized in teaching aviation politeness.

Case Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Aviation Politeness Structures	9	100.0%	0	0.0%	90	100.0%
Teaching strategies in Aviation Politeness	5	5.6%	85	94.4%	90	100.0%

Student interviews

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Table 4 showed the results of the interview for Students 'Preferences on Types of Politeness Structures. While statement about structure "Will / Would you..., (please)?" received the highest level of preference (N=9; P= 24.1%, P of C=100.0%), statement about structure "Do infinitive / Infinitive + please" received the lowest level of preference (N=1; P= 2.7%, P of C=11.1%). This presented that students liked structure "Will / Would you..., (please)?" than structure "Do infinitive / Infinitive + please" because of its polite meaning in the former.

Table 4: Students 'Preferences on Types of Politeness Structures

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
Politeness Structures	1. Will / Would you..., (please)?	9	24.1%	100.0%
	2. Can / Could you..., (please)?	8	21.4%	88.9%
	3. Do / Would you mind ... if...?	6	16.0%	66.7%
	4. Would you like + N / to + V?	5	14.4%	60.0%
	5. I suggest you / we + V / I recommend + V-ing	4	10.7%	44.4%
	6. What / How about..?	4	10.7%	44.4%
	7. Do infinitive / Infinitive + please	1	2.7%	11.1%
Total		37	100.0%	415.6%

Teacher interviews

Table 5 proved that all of five teachers prioritized the strategy of giving brief explanations about politeness structures. This could be explained that they concentrated on directing the students to the correct structures from the beginning, to avoid breakdown communications later. Four among them liked giving stimulating situations to ask the students to apply these structures through the performance of role-play. There were two strategies of correction during the students' performance. Two teachers chose the way of indicating students' errors and providing the correct forms, whereas, three teachers chose the way of giving students' prompt self correction by repeating exactly what they said. For them, self-correct strategy in communications would be more effective and bring good results to face – saving.

Table 5: Teachers 's strategies in instructing Politeness in Aviation Communications

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
Teachers strategies	1. Give brief explanations about politeness structures	5	35.7%	100.0%
	2. Give stimulating situations	4	28.6%	80.0%
	3. Indicate students' errors and provide the correct forms	2	14.3%	40.0%
	4. Give students' prompt self correction by repeating exactly what they said	3	21.4%	60.0%
Total		14	100.0%	280.0%

4.3. Classroom observation results

The classroom observation sought to teaching and learning progress that focused on five issues. They are students' perception, students' attitudes, students' desire, students' preference on Types of Politeness Structures, and teachers' strategies in instructing students in politeness in aviation communications. These classroom observations received the results, on the side of students, as follow: (i) Students had positive perceptions and attitudes towards politeness in aviation communications; (ii) Students had desire to communicate politely in any stimulating situation; (iii) Students preferred many popular and simple structures, such as "Will / Would you..., (please)?" ; "Can / Could you..., (please)?" ; "Would you like + N / to + V?" rather than complex structures, such as "Do / Would you mind ... if...?" ; "I suggest you / we + V / I recommend + V-ing", or less polite or impolite structure such as "Do infinitive / Infinitive + please"; " What / How about..? "; (iv) Students mostly liked to receive teachers' instructions for Politeness in Aviation Communications.

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On the side of teachers, these classroom observations received the results as follow: (i) Teachers gave brief explanations about politeness structures then encouraged students to role playing; (ii) Teachers supervised and helped students with corrections (directly or indirectly)

5. CONCLUSION

The study, after a process of data collecting and analyzing, and finding and discussing, could obtain some conclusions. First, the study discovered that politeness in aviation passenger service communications was very important and vital. Second, there were noticeable issues in expressing politeness through speech act of request as follow: (i) English does not typically begin requests with “*request*” or “*ask*” but instead uses conventional polite structures; (ii) “*Would/Could you...?*” is the most frequently used and appropriate polite structure in professional contexts; (iii) Bare imperatives (e.g., *Fasten your seatbelt.*) are inappropriate in passenger services; (iv) Care should be taken in using structures with *mind* correctly; (v) Due to hierarchical and social relationships, requests must maintain polite and formal tones. From a pragmatic perspective, understanding language in use requires consideration of context, speaker-hearer relationships, and implied meanings. Therefore, language teaching must situate utterances within authentic communicative contexts. Third, role-play with stimulated scenario, after teachers’ explaining key structures, gave students interests in learning. The findings of the study can serve as a valuable resource for teachers and students in teaching and learning. However, the study remains limited in scope and represents only an initial exploration of polite English usage in aviation communications. In future study, the author hopes to expand more population and sampling. Further research is needed to examine politeness in other speech acts and professional contexts to better support English communications in Vietnam’s ongoing international integration.

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